

Supplementary tables and figures to the following paper to be published in Journal Dairy Science 2023:

Genotypic characterization of *Staphylococcus chromogenes* and *Staphylococcus simulans* from Swedish cases of bovine sub-clinical mastitis

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Supplementary Table 1. Command line arguments for bioinformatics programs used for analyses of the genomes of bovine milk isolates of *Staphylococcus chromogenes* and *Staphylococcus simulans*

Program	Arguments
Pilon	Bowtie2-build -f -very-sensitive-local Bowtie2 -x -phred33 -very-sensitive-local -no-unal
Prokka	<i>S. chromogenes</i> : --addgenes --genus Staphylococcus --species chromogenes --kingdom Bacteria \ --proteins references/GCF_900458195.1_41315_F01_genomic_Schromogenes.gbff <i>S. simulans</i> : --addgenes --genus Staphylococcus --species simulans --kingdom Bacteria \ --proteins references/GCF_001559115.2_ASM155911v2_genomic_Ssimulans.gbff \
SPAdes	--careful
Trimmomatic	-phred33 ILLUMINACLIP:\$illum_adaptors_path:2:30:5:1:TRUE LEADING:3 TRAILING:3 MAXINFO:40:0.2 MINLEN:36

	Cysteine protease (Staphopain)	<i>sspA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Cysteine protease (Staphopain)	<i>sspB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
		<i>sspC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sspD</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sspE</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sspF</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Hyaluronate lyase	<i>hysA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Lipase	<i>lip</i>	100	100	100	100	100	97.1	0
		<i>geh</i>	28.5	0	83.3	0	0	29.5	100
	Serine protease	<i>splA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>splB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>splC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>splD</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>splE</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>splF</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	66.1
	Staphylocoagulase	<i>coa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Staphylokinase	<i>sak</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Thermonuclease	<i>nuc</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Von Willebrand factor-binding protein	<i>vWbp</i>	100	100	100	100	100	98.1	0
Host immune evasion	Arginine catabolic metabolic element (ACME)	<i>arcA</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Capsule	<i>capA</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	95.8
		<i>capB</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	100
		<i>capC</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	100
		<i>capD</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	100
		<i>capE</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	0
		<i>capF</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	0
		<i>capG</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	0
		<i>capH</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	12.4	3.4
		<i>capI</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	0
		<i>capJ</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	13.3	100
		<i>capK</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	1.7
		<i>capL</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	0
		<i>capM</i>	0	0	16.7	0	0	15.2	100
		<i>capN</i>	100	100	100	100	100	96.2	0
	<i>capO</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	98.3	
	<i>capP</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	Chemotaxis inhibitory protein of Staphylococcus	<i>chp</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Staphylococcal complement inhibitor	<i>sen</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	0
	Staphylococcal protein A	<i>spa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	95.8
Staphylococcal binder of immunoglobulin	<i>sbi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	0	
Iron uptake and metabolism	Iron-regulated surface determinant	<i>isdA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.7
		<i>isdB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	5.1
		<i>isdC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
		<i>isdD</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>isdE</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
		<i>isdF</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	55.9
		<i>isdG</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

		<i>isdH</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>isdI</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Import and iron release Staphyloferrin A	<i>htsA</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	82.2
		<i>htsB</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
		<i>htsC</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	NPQTN-specific sortase B	<i>srtB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
	Synthesis and export; Staphyloferrin B	<i>sbnA</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
		<i>sbnB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnD</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnE</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnF</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnG</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnH</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>sbnI</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Synthesis and export; Staphyloferrin A	<i>sfaA</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
		<i>sfaB</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
		<i>sfaC</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
		<i>sfaD</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Import and iron release; Staphyloferrin B synthesis related	<i>sirA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	4.8	0
		<i>sirB</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	0
		<i>sirC</i>	100	100	100	100	100	98.1	0
Hemolysin	Alpha hemolysin	<i>hly/ hla</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Beta hemolysin	<i>hly</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	0
	Delta hemolysin	<i>hly</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	33.9
	Gamma hemolysin	<i>hlyA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>hlyB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>hlyC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Leukocidin	Leukocidin M	<i>lukM</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		<i>lukF-like</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Leukotoxins	Panton-Valentine leukocidin	<i>lukS-PV</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>lukF-PV</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Leukotoxin D	<i>lukD</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Leukotoxin E	<i>lukE</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TSST	Toxic shock syndrome toxin	<i>Tsst</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Exfoliate toxin	Exfoliate toxin type A	<i>eta</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Exfoliate toxin type B	<i>etb</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Exfoliate toxin type C	<i>etc</i>	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Exfoliate toxin type D	<i>etd</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Secretion system	Type VII secretion system	<i>esaA</i>	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	0
	Type VII secretion system	<i>esaB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	10.5	0
		<i>esaC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		<i>essa</i>	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	0
		<i>essB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	0
		<i>essC</i>	0	0	0	0	0	7.6	0
		<i>esxA</i>	0	0	0	0	7.7	2.9	0.8
<i>esxB</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	PSM alpha	<i>PSMα1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Phenol soluble modulins (PSM)	PSM alpha	<i>PSMα2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		<i>PSMα3</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		<i>PSMα4</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		<i>PSMα6</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		PSM beta	<i>PSMβ1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	44.1
			<i>PSMβ2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			<i>PSMβ3</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			<i>PSMβ4</i>	100	100	100	100	84.6	85.7	0.8
			<i>PSMβ5</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>PSMβ6</i>	0		0	0	0	0	0	0		
Enterotoxin	Enterotoxin A	<i>sea</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin B	<i>seb</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin C	<i>sec</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin D	<i>sed</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin E	<i>see</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin G	<i>sef</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin H	<i>seg</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin I	<i>sei</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin J	<i>sej</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like K	<i>selk</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like L	<i>sell</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like M	<i>selm</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like N	<i>seln</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like O	<i>selo</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like P	<i>selp</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like Q	<i>selq</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like R	<i>selr</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like U	<i>selu</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin-like V	<i>selv</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Enterotoxin Yent1	<i>yent1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Enterotoxin Yent2	<i>yent2</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1.0	0		
Exotoxin	S. exotoxin 1	<i>set1</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 2	<i>set2</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 3	<i>set3</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 4	<i>set4</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 5	<i>set5</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 6	<i>set6</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 7	<i>set7</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 8	<i>set8</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 9	<i>set9</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 10	<i>set10</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 11	<i>set11</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 12	<i>set12</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 13	<i>set13</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 15	<i>set15</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 16	<i>set16</i>	0	0	0	0	0	6.7	0	
	S. exotoxin 17	<i>set17</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 18	<i>set18</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 19	<i>set19</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	S. exotoxin 20	<i>set20</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1.9	0	
	S. exotoxin 21	<i>set21</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

S. exotoxin 22	<i>set22</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 23	<i>set23</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 24	<i>set24</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 25	<i>set25</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 26	<i>set26</i>	100	100	100	100	100	88.6	0
S. exotoxin 30	<i>set30</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 31	<i>set31</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 32	<i>set32</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 33	<i>set33</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 34	<i>set34</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 35	<i>set35</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 36	<i>set36</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 37	<i>set37</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 38	<i>set38</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 39	<i>set39</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S. exotoxin 40	<i>set40</i>	0	0	0	0	0	15.2	0
Mean (SD) numbers of VF		27.3 (0.6)	27.2 (0.6)	29.0 (5.4)	26.0 (0)	27.0 (0.6)	29.6 (5.4)	32.4 (1.4)
Min-max numbers of VF		26-28	26- 28	26- 40	26- 26	26- 28	25-45	28-35

Supplementary Figure 1. Phylogeny and population structure of bovine milk isolates of *Staphylococcus chromogenes*. A. Maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree of sequence types (STs) (n=47) with the identified clusters (n=7) in grey shades. B. eBURST analysis of STs, with each colored box representing a ST (founders in yellow-green) and the numbers between STs showing the number of allelic differences.

1b

Cluster VII

Cluster VI

Cluster II

Cluster III

Cluster V

Cluster IV

Cluster I

0.01

1a

Supplementary Figure 2. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of bovine milk isolates of *Staphylococcus chromogenes* (n=105) constructed using the core genome identified by Roary, with identified clusters (n=7) and the bootstrap values.

Supplementary Figure 3. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of bovine milk isolates of *Staphylococcus simulans* (n=118) constructed using the core genome identified by Roary, with identified clusters (n=3) and subclusters (n=5) and the bootstrap values.

